

FAIRmat Newsletter

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Editorial

Welcome to the sixth FAIRmat Newsletter!

As the year comes to an end, much like enjoying the festive atmosphere of the holiday season, let's take a moment to acknowledge the many accomplishments of the past few months. This edition highlights significant strides made by the FAIRmat initiative in advancing FAIR research data management (RDM) in materials science.

We've expanded NOMAD's capabilities, submitted our interim report to the DFG, and engaged with the community through events like the FAIR-DI Conference 2024. We are particularly excited about the growing adoption of the NOMAD plugin system, providing users and data stewards with the means to customize and extend NOMAD's functionality to suit their specific needs. This community-driven approach is crucial for building a robust and adaptable data infrastructure, and for continuing to push the boundaries of RDM in materials science together.

We encourage you to explore the articles in this newsletter and engage with the FAIRmat community. We wish you all a Happy New Year filled with success for FAIRmat and exciting scientific discoveries!

Silvana Botti

Co-spokesperson and leader of Area C: Computation

FAIRmat news

FAIRmat at the EOSC Symposium 2024

The [EOSC Symposium 2024](#) marked an important milestone in establishing the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Federation. A key highlight was the launch of the first [EOSC EU Node](#), which will serve as a model for future nodes. Notable participants included European officials and representatives from the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI), who emphasized the importance of alignment and collaboration between European and national infrastructures. Claudia Draxl, FAIRmat's spokesperson, delivered a scientific keynote entitled "FAIR, what else?", highlighting the importance of sustainable practices in research and responsible data management. A recording of the keynote presentation is available [online](#).

Datasets and workflow tools from the FAIRmat PIs

In recent months, FAIRmat PIs have demonstrated remarkable progress in utilizing and expanding the NOMAD infrastructure:

Miguel Marques and Silvana Botti (Area C: Computation) uploaded the [Alexandria Database](#), a massive dataset of ~4.5M DFT calculations, increasing the entries in NOMAD's central repository by a stunning 35%.

Tristan Bereau (Area C: Computation) and his student Luis Walter have built a module to link their domain-specific workflows with the NOMAD API to perform high-throughput molecular dynamics simulations. This work, [recently published](#) in the Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling, demonstrates how to leverage NOMAD for FAIR-data management in a field, where the simulations are poorly shared, are deficiently reproducible, and lack provenance.

FAIRmat co-organizes the FAIR-DI Conference 2024

The FAIR-DI European Conference on Data Intelligence 2024, co-organized by FAIRmat, took place from October 27 to 30 in Karlsruhe, Germany. The event brought together experts from different fields to discuss advances in research data management, artificial intelligence, and large language models in materials science.

About [100 contributions](#), highlighted recent advances of databases and tools, with examples from materials synthesis, artificial photosynthesis, excited-state calculations, etc. All contributions introduced innovative methods or improved capabilities for exploiting large datasets, enabling faster and more efficient discoveries. During the conference, the FAIR-DI Award for outstanding FAIR-aligned data handling in a PhD thesis was given to Lena Pilz from KIT.

Gian-Marco Rignanese (left) presents the FAIR-DI Award to Lena Pilz (right).

Project milestones

FAIRmat submits progress report

FAIRmat has recently submitted its interim report to the German Research Foundation ([DFG](#)). The report outlines major progress in developing NOMAD, our single integrated, extensible, distributed FAIR research data management service. Highlights include the development of tools such as NOMAD Oasis and NOMAD CAMELS, and the engagement of the community through workshops, training sessions, and conferences.

Key milestones include extending NOMAD's support for 141 file formats specific to data from materials synthesis, experimental characterization, and simulation codes, and developing a plugin mechanism to provide customization and modularity of specialized tools in local NOMAD Oasis installations. You can read the publicly available short summary of the report, along with those of other NFDI consortia, at this [link](#).

Status of our integrated, extensible, and distributed RDM service NOMAD.

The NOMAD materials processing plugin

The NOMAD materials processing plugin integrates with the NOMAD platform to manage materials synthesis data according to the FAIR principles. It provides NOMAD schemas for materials synthesis processes. Built on the Chemical Methods Ontology (CHMO), it serves as a community-standard tool, offering shared schemas and sections for structuring data. Supported techniques include vapor deposition methods (e.g., MBE, PLD, MOVPE) and solution processing. Corresponding tools for bulk crystal growth and polymerization are under development.

By offering a bottom-up approach and ease of use, the plugin enables researchers to document and share their data more effectively. This is evidenced by the widespread use of the vapor deposition schema by 12 research groups across 5 countries. Version 1.0 is available on [GitHub](#) and is published on [Zenodo](#). You can install this plugin on your NOMAD Oasis or test it on the [example Oasis](#).

The FAIRmat infrastructure

Markus Scheidgen
Infrastructure coordinator

What are NOMAD plugins?

NOMAD plugins are modular extensions that customize and extend NOMAD's functionality. These plugins can add support for new data types, file formats, data processing, search interfaces, example data, or new APIs. By developing plugins, data stewards can tailor NOMAD to the specific needs of their peers. We build an ecosystem, where plugins can be shared to integrate communities and harmonize RDM practices.

The main benefits of using NOMAD plugins.

Empowering the community with more NOMAD customization options

NOMAD, the extensible data infrastructure at the heart of FAIRmat, is committed to a bottom-up approach. Users and data stewards can actively shape NOMAD's functionality by developing plugins. We offer a variety of plugin entry points to accommodate diverse needs, including support for new data types and file formats, data processing, custom search interfaces, and more.

To facilitate plugin development, we have significantly updated our [plugin documentation](#). It now provides in-depth explanations of all available plugin entry points. We provide [a plugin project template](#) that lets plugin developers start faster and produce more consistent plugins.

On top of schemas, parsers, normalizers, and search apps, we also included two new plugin entry points:

- **Example uploads** allow plugin developers to provide data that showcase the features of their plugin. It is a good opportunity for data stewards to introduce their peers to RDM via blueprints for organizing data.
- **Custom APIs** plugins can also introduce backend functionality, which opens new possibilities to

implement automation and integration with other on-site systems.

Beyond plugin development, we are excited to introduce NOMAD distributions. These customizable NOMAD installations allow Oasis administrators to select and deploy only the necessary plugins, streamlining deployments and reducing overhead. NOMAD distributions are managed through Git projects, enabling automated builds and updates via CI/CD pipelines.

To foster a thriving community and ensure the long-term sustainability of NOMAD, we established a central official NOMAD distribution. This distribution will serve as a registry for official NOMAD and FAIRmat plugins as well as a platform for showcasing and sharing third-party contributions. It is used to deploy the central NOMAD installation as well as our test Oasis. We also developed [a template for distribution projects](#) to aid Oasis admins. The Oasis installation is now integrated into the distributions, which allows users to configure, build, and deploy Oasis from a single GitHub project.

Various domains within our project have successfully adopted the plugin system. This includes not only specialized plugins for computational materials-science codes or NeXus files, but also more general community plugins for measurements and materials processing. The community plugins are meant to be extended further by more specialized plugins. By migrating functionality from the core NOMAD codebase to individual plugin projects, we have significantly streamlined the maintenance process and improved the overall flexibility of the platform. This transition not only benefits our FAIRmat project, but also demonstrates the potential for the NOMAD ecosystem to scale and evolve beyond our initial scope.

NOMAD plugin entry points: Customizable extensions for your NOMAD Oasis installation.

Meet our users

Lena Mittmann

Doctoral student, Technical University of Denmark (DTU)

What is your research focus?

I have studied chemistry and am currently a doctoral researcher at Technical University of Denmark (DTU) in Andrea Crovetto's research group. Our group focuses on discovering new materials within the versatile class of phosphosulfides through high-throughput synthesis using physical vapor deposition (PVD). We explore this unique class of materials by combining experimental and theoretical approaches.

I utilize combinatorial thin-film synthesis via PVD to synthesize and characterize these materials to determine their suitability as semiconductors for applications such as optoelectronics. Additionally, one of my primary responsibilities is to implement and customize NOMAD to meet the needs of our research group. Due to our combinatorial synthesis routine, we generate substantial amount of data, and NOMAD allows us to track, collect, and analyze these data efficiently.

What challenges did you face in applying the FAIR data principles and starting with NOMAD?

During my chemistry studies, I did not learn about the FAIR principles. It was only when I started my PhD that I became aware of them. For my master's thesis, I relied on a handwritten lab journal. I believe that incorporating FAIR data principles into the curriculum would benefit students and research itself as these principles increasingly influence research practices.

One of the main challenges we faced when starting with NOMAD was building our entire laboratory from scratch, which meant we were balancing lab construction while implementing NOMAD. However, this presented a significant advantage. Our laboratory development follows a step by step process, enabling us to integrate appropriate workflows directly into NOMAD without investing additional effort in translating existing workflows. My programming experience was limited when I started with NOMAD. However, I am expanding my knowledge as I work on customizing our NOMAD Oasis. I am incredibly grateful for the support from the FAIRmat team, particularly Hampus Näsström.

What is your group's research data management (RDM) strategy, and how is FAIRmat supporting you?

As mentioned, we focus on high-throughput combinatorial synthesis, generating huge amounts of data. From the outset, it was clear that we needed a digital RDM tool to expedite data analysis and avoid potential bottlenecks caused by limited resources. We automate as many steps in our daily research as possible. We use NOMAD to plan our experiments, as an electronic lab notebook, and to store our data directly alongside the digital twins of our corresponding samples. This approach ensures that all our data are consolidated in one location, making them easily accessible to all relevant group members.

Since our research focuses on discovering new materials, it is unlikely that we will test them in applications. Therefore, collecting data according to the FAIR principles is essential for sharing them with collaborators who can later put these materials into practical use.

Comment by our expert

Hampus Näsström

Developer in Area A: Synthesis

One of my responsibilities is to support users, including Lena, by installing, customizing, and establishing NOMAD and NOMAD Oasis within their research groups. It is impressive to see Lena's progress in the past two years by tailoring NOMAD to meet the needs of her colleagues and herself.

We have established weekly meetings to discuss recent developments on her end. During these sessions, we address challenges and collaborate to create a strategy that fully represents their experimental workflow, from planning experiments to data analysis and visualization on NOMAD. We are working on implementing this strategy step by step into their NOMAD Oasis.

Working with Lena has also greatly benefited my work. Consulting with her helps me better understand our users' needs, identify gaps in our documentation, and determine where we need to be more explicit to empower all users to work independently on installing, customizing, and using NOMAD as their RDM tool.

Opinion article

Kevin Jablonka

Task leader in Area E: Use Cases

Building tomorrow's science on yesterday's knowledge: the LLM bridge

A significant opportunity cost in scientific research stems from losing experience when people leave research groups, forcing others to rebuild this knowledge from scratch. Substantial value could be gained if such knowledge were not lost but instead democratized.¹ This drives the motivation behind research data infrastructures and recent efforts to collect new datasets through large-scale simulations and high-throughput experimental campaigns.

Interestingly, research has predominantly relied on artifacts published as scientific articles to inform experiments. Pragmatically speaking, the scale of data in scientific literature drastically overshadows the number of structured datasets available in repositories.² More importantly, science has a long-tail character³—research topics are diverse, and each study differs slightly from prior works. This diversity makes building research data infrastructure (and high-throughput campaigns) challenging—but it is precisely what makes large language models (LLMs) so appealing.⁴

My group focuses on utilizing such frontier models for materials science because they are the first models showing genuine sparks of ability to perform well on tasks they have not been explicitly trained on—and doing things for the first time is at the heart of science. Additionally, science is living: our understanding of what is important in a materials design project evolves over time.⁵ As we gather more information, we refine our understanding and often realize that we should have gathered different or additional information. Facing this reality is only possible with highly adaptable tools.⁶

During my PhD, I had the urge to build new datasets using data mining techniques. However, with the tools available then, this would have consumed my entire PhD to create one particular dataset. With recent advances in LLMs, much of this work has been reduced to a master's thesis scope. This reduction in effort is particularly appealing as it enables the creation of evolving datasets whose schemas we can adjust as we learn more about the system. However, challenges remain. The literature contains gaps by commission and omission⁷ - which we can address, at least partially, with physics-informed validation. Additionally, current systems still struggle to

effectively extract information from plots and figures and automatically create links to datasets across repositories.⁸

Yet, we are moving toward a stage where creating and maintaining bespoke datasets for many aspects in the long tail of scientific research will become routine. Interestingly, NOMAD will be crucial in creating and maintaining these datasets. For instance, we are currently running a campaign using a NOMAD Oasis to collect feedback on extraction results from an LLM.

This convergence of AI capabilities with research platforms represents a significant step toward preserving and democratizing scientific knowledge. Leveraging these tools, we are not just creating datasets; we are building a more resilient, living, and interconnected scientific ecosystem that - hopefully - can better retain and utilize the collective knowledge of researchers across generations.

References:

1. [K. M. Jablonka *et al.*, Nat. Chem. 14, 365 \(2022\).](#)
2. [M. Schilling-Wilhelmi *et al.*, Chem. Soc. Rev. \(2025\), in print.](#)
3. [P. B. Heidorn, Libr. Trends 57, 280 \(2008\).](#)
4. [A. D. White, Nat. Rev. Chem. 7, 457 \(2023\).](#)
5. [S. Moosavi *et al.*, J. Am. Chem. Soc. 142, 20273 \(2020\).](#)
6. [C. Ré, AI trends that I unironically love, online, \(2021\).](#)
7. [M. Strasser, Extracting knowledge from literature, online, \(2021\).](#)
8. [D. Ongari *et al.*, J. Chem. Eng. Data 67, 1743 \(2022\).](#)

Outreach and training

During the second half of 2024, we have engaged with our community in various events and occasions. We have continued our [tutorial series](#) with editions 14 and 15, and furthered our collaboration with [technology partners](#) during two workshops on data exchange and storage in [ellipsometry](#) and [Raman spectroscopy](#), respectively. Our team has presented FAIRmat and NOMAD at various international conferences, such as the 8th Asian Materials Data Symposium ([AMDS2024](#)) in China, the European Microscopy Congress 2024 ([emc24](#)) in Copenhagen, and the 18th International Congress on Catalysis ([ICC](#)) in Lyon. We also gave several presentations and webinars at events organized by our collaborators and community members.

Two highlights of the last months have been our hackathon on [FAIR Data Management of Spectroscopy Simulations](#), organized by Area C: Computation, and the [Fifth FAIRmat](#)

[Users Meeting](#) in Berlin. During the three-day hackathon, the participants learned how to create and develop new NOMAD parsers and how to use the standard NOMAD schema. Parsers are essential tools in RDM, acting as translators between files and structured data schemas. The participants could understand, use, and extend the standard data schema defined for simulations in NOMAD. The Fifth FAIRmat Users Meeting showcased the growing community committed to RDM according to the FAIR data principles. It offered a full-day program with invited talks by our users and collaborators in the morning, while the afternoon focused on hands-on workshops on NOMAD and direct exchange with our domain experts. We are thankful to all participants for their active engagement and contributions.

You can find detailed reports about our events on the [FAIRmat news page](#), where we regularly post updates on our outreach activities.

Upcoming events

In 2025, we will continue our outreach activities to foster community building and integration, following our bottom-up approach to improving the scientific ecosystem in RDM. We have already secured booth spaces at three conferences where you can find us in the exhibition area:

- [DPG Spring Meeting of the Condensed Matter Section](#), March 16-21, 2025, in Regensburg, Germany.
- [European Materials Research Society \(E-MRS\) 2025 Spring Meeting](#), May 26-30, 2025, in Strasbourg, France.
- [Psi-K 2025 Conference](#), August 25-28, 2025, in Lausanne, Switzerland.

In addition to these conferences, check our [events page](#) regularly. We are constantly adding various events related

New members in the FAIRmat team!

Sharat Patil

Development Team
Area E

Natalia Slepenco

Event Management
Area F

Recent publications

- M. Schilling-Wilhelmi, M. Ríos-García, S. Shabih, M. V. Gil, S. Miret, C. T. Koch, J. A. Márquez, and K. M. Jablonka, [From Text to Insight: Large Language Models for Materials Science Data Extraction](#), *Chem. Soc. Rev.* (2025), in print.
- T. Berau, L. J. Walter, and J. F. Rudzinski, [Martignac: Computational Workflows for Reproducible, Traceable, and Composable Coarse-Grained Martini Simulations](#), *J. Chem. Inf. Model.* **64**, 9413 (2024).
- Y. Zimmermann et al., [Reflections from the 2024 Large Language Model \(LLM\) Hackathon for Applications in Materials Science and Chemistry](#), preprint (2024).
- L. M. Ghiringhelli, L. Sbailò, Á. Fekete, M. Scheidgen, and M. Scheffler, [Choosing AI analysis tools and enacting their reproducibility: the NOMAD AI toolkit](#), Section 3.4 in S. Bauer et al. Roadmap on Data-Centric Materials Science, *Modelling Simul. Mater. Sci. Eng.* **32**, 063301 (2024).
- A. Moshantaf, M. Wesemann, S. Beinlich, H. Junkes, J. Schumann, B. Alkan, P. Kube, C. P. Marshall, N. Pfister, and A. Trunschke, [Advancing catalysis research through FAIR data principles implemented in a local data infrastructure – a case study of an automated test reactor](#), *Catal. Sci. Technol.* **14**, 6186 (2024).
- M. L. Evans et al., [Developments and applications of the OPTIMADE API for materials discovery, design, and data exchange](#), *Digit. Discov.* **3**, 1509 (2024).

The full list of our publications and invited talks can be found on our website.

Stay in touch

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NOMAD Discord!

Join our NOMAD Discord, where you can connect with fellow researchers, share ideas, and get answers.

Selected shots from the last few months

Some photos from our most recent Project and Users Meetings.

There's always time for culinary exploration.

FAIRmat's event team meets and greets NOMAD users.

Levi and the FAIRmat rollup ready for some photos.

Discussions, talks, and coffee.

More talks and definitly more coffee.

FAIRmat is always ready for coffee.